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An intrinsic link between the EMT program and aging in human cells.

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Vimentin was among the gene whose transcripts was produced in largest quantity in the aging CD8+ lymphocyte. Vimentin expression differentiated the newborn and adult or aging CD8+ lymphocyte. Zeb2 but not Zeb1 was enriched in aging CD8+ primary T cells. Col6a2 was enriched in newborn cells but Col6a1 was enriched in aging CD8+ T cells. In the myeloid compartment, SNAI1 expression characterized the aging monocyte.